

The hydrophilid larva consumed up to 6.7 fifth-instar caseworm larvae daily, but only 2-3 of first- or second-instar larvae. Regardless of age, the dytiscid preferred older prey. It was also more voracious, consuming more than 11

fifth-instar caseworm larvae daily.

Aquatic predators may explain why caseworm is more prevalent in rainfed than in irrigated wetlands. Rice irrigated from rivers, reservoirs, or canals would already contain dytiscids

and hydrophilids. Delayed dispersal flights of predators to rainfed fields could allow greater survival of the caseworm, which attacks a young crop before the aquatic predators can initiate a new infestation. *S*

Major insect pests of rice in Cuba

R. Meneses-Carbonell, Rice Experiment Station "Sur del Jibaro," Sancti Spiritus, Cuba

Rice planthopper *Sogatodes orizicola*, the hoja blanca virus vector, is the principal insect pest of rice in Cuba (see table). Life cycle of adult males is 14-24 d; that of females, 27-31 d. The cycle from egg to adult is about 25 d. *S. orizicola* needs high temperatures (25-27°C) for optimum development.

Higher insect activity and population densities are Apr-Nov.

The most difficult insect pest to control is the rice water weevil, with a 50-d cycle from oviposition to adult emergence. Adults live an average 714 d. *Lissorhoptrus brevirostris* population is highest in Apr-Nov, with large damages to ricefields.

Other important pests are rice stink bug *Oebalus insularis* and fall armyworm *Spodoptera frugiperda*.

Other insects are sporadic pests of rice in Cuba. *S*

First meiotic chromosomes of male *Nephotettix malayanus*

R. C. Saxena, International Centre of Insect Physiology and Ecology (ICIPE), Kenya, and International Rice Research Institute (IRRI); and A. A. Barrion, Institute of Biological Sciences, University of the Philippines at Los Baños

During growth phase of spermatogenesis in the green leafhopper *N. malayanus*, the primary spermatocytes undergo the first meiotic division. At diakinesis (Fig. 1a), the maximum condensation and coiling of holokinetic chromosomes results in 6 synapsed homologs plus a univalent X-body.

The male *N. malayanus* therefore has the normal diploid complement, $2n = 13$ ($6I_A + X$). The prospective haploid sperm cells are of two types: ($6I_A + X$) and ($6I_A$). The darkly stained, unpaired X-chromosome measured 1.18μ in length and width, and was usually isolated from the bivalent autosomes.

In pachytene analysis of meiotic chromosomes, the mean total

Major insect pests of lowland rice in Cuba, 1976-84.

Scientific name	Growth stage	Damage	Infestation (%)
<i>Sogatodes orizicola</i> (Muir) (Homoptera: Delphacidae)	Emergence to maximum tillering	Leaf sucking (nymphs and adults)	2-12
<i>Sogatodes cubanus</i> (Crawford) (Homoptera: Delphacidae)	Emergence to maximum tillering	Leaf sucking (nymphs and adults)	
<i>Lissorhoptrus brevirostris</i> (Suffr.) (Coleoptera: Curculionidae)	Emergence to maximum tillering	Root feeding (larvae) Leaf feeding on leaves (adults)	10-28
<i>Spodoptera frugiperda</i> (F. Smith) (Lepidoptera: Noctuidae)	Emergence to maximum tillering	Leaf feeding (larvae) May eat entire plant	6-10
<i>Hortensia similis</i> (Walk.) (Homoptera: Cicadellidae)	Emergence to maximum tillering	Leaf sucking (nymphs and adults)	
<i>Draeculacephala cubana</i> (M & B) (Homoptera: Cicadellidae)	Emergence to maximum tillering	Leaf sucking (nymphs and adults)	
<i>Hydrellia</i> sp. (Diptera: Ephydriidae)	Emergence to panicle initiation	Feeding on tissue along the inner margins of emerging leaves (larvae)	New pests
<i>Diatraea saccharalis</i> (F.) (Lepidoptera: Pyralidae)	Emergence to panicle initiation	Feeding within the stem, severing the vascular system (larvae)	
<i>Caulopsis cuspidatus</i> (Scud.) (Orthoptera: Acrididae)	Panicle initiation to heading	Feeding on the leaf blade	
<i>Conocephalus</i> [= <i>Xiphidium</i>] <i>fasciatus</i> (De Geer) (Orthoptera: Tettigoniidae)	Panicle initiation to heading	Leaf feeding (nymphs and adults)	
<i>Conocephaloides obscurelus</i> (De Geer) (Orthoptera: Tettigoniidae)	Panicle initiation to heading	Leaf feeding (nymphs and adults)	
<i>Schistocerca pallens</i> (Thunb.) (Orthoptera: Acrididae)	Panicle initiation to heading	Defoliate plants	
<i>Oebalus insularis</i> (Stal) (Hemiptera: Pentatomidae)	Milk stage	Sucking each grain (nymphs and adults)	3-17

1. Chromosomes of male *N. malayanus* at a) diakinesis showing $2n = 13$, and b) metaphase I. Spontaneous aberration may result in c) an agmatoploid cell with $2n = 19$ ($9II + X$). IRRI, 1985-86. Arrow indicates the sex chromosome. Magnification 1500X (oil immersion).

chromatin length (142 mm) ranged from 10 mm to 36 mm (Fig. 2). The X-body was 9 mm long while the nucleolar organizing region (NOR) was 26 mm long. The relative mean length of the 7 linkage groups was 0.063 mm; NOR measured 0.183 mm.

These chromosomes condensed maximally during premetaphase, with these diameters: 4.1 μ , 3.5 μ , 3.5 μ , 2.9 μ , 2.6 μ , 2.4 μ , and 2.3 μ . One autosome was distinctly large (4.12 μ long and 3.5 μ wide) and was termed macro-autosome. Later, during metaphase I (Fig. 1b), the X-body fused

2. Camera lucida drawing of pachytene chromosomes of *N. malayanus* and their idiogram. IRRI, 1985-86. Sex chromosome is indicated by an arrow. Magnification 1250X (oil immersion).

with the autosomes at the equatorial plate. The corresponding chromosome volumes were 0.029 μ^3 (NOR), 0.018 μ^3 (NOR), 0.018 μ^3 , 0.01 μ^3 , 0.005 μ^3 , and 0.0007 μ^3 (X).

N. malayanus has a mean meiotic index of 0.56, mean number of meiocytes 203, and mean number of nonmeiocytes 157.

During diakinesis, spontaneous chromosomal aberrations were shown by cells. In 100 cells, 10% had reduced chromosome numbers and 5% had increased chromosome numbers (Fig. 1c). $\mathcal{S}$

Population dynamics of the brown planthopper (BPH) in irrigated lowland areas of West Java, Indonesia

K. Sogawa, A. Kusmayadi, Y. Raksadinata, Soekirno, F. Natanegara, and T.R. Djatmono, Indonesia-Japan Joint Programme on Food Crop Protection, Directorate of Food Crop Protection, P.O. Box 36, Pasarminggu, Jakarta, Indonesia

Population dynamics of the BPH were studied in six consecutive crop seasons (1983 dry season to 1985-86 wet season).

BPH- susceptible, high-yielding Pelita I/1 was planted in 10- $\times$ 10-m paddy plots. BPH population density and composition were visually counted weekly in 20- to 210-hill samples, depending on growth stage. Percentage of brachyptery was monitored weekly by sampling 5th-instar nymphs.

Although BPH populations varied considerably across the crop seasons, insect generations within a season more or less overlapped, a basic pattern of BPH population dynamics. Three ecological stages were associated with wing dimorphism (see figure):

Immigration: BPH population was initiated in newly transplanted rice fields with the immigration of a small number of macropterous adults. Immigration usually started at 3 wk after transplanting (WT) and was discontinuous throughout vegetative growth.

Basic trend of BPH population development in irrigated lowland ricefields in Jatisari, West Java, and important components and stages of a population cycle. G-0 to G-3 = generation, B = brachypterous, M = macropterous.

Colonization: Nymphs from the immigrant founders appeared at 5-6 WT. The population increased strikingly when second-generation nymphs emerged, reaching its peak at heading to flowering 9-11 WT. Before the surge in nymph population, brachypterous females emerged at 6-8 WT, indicating the shift of generation.

Wing form monitoring showed that

almost all the adults that emerged before 8 WT were brachypterous, indicating that first-generation nymphs from macropterous immigrants emerged mostly as brachyptera to contribute directly to colony growth.

Emigration: Adults emerging 10 WT from the peak nymph population were predominantly macropterous and emigrated. The population usually